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25 Interesting Facts About Akhmatova

Israilova Gulnara Mamadzhonovna

Lecturer at the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: This article tells interesting facts about Akhmatova. She was actively persecuted, not allowed to publish, and her relatives were persecuted and harassed. Her work reflects all the suffering that not only people who were considered "enemies of the people" by the ruling party went through, but also their families.

Keywords: relatives were subjected to, hard life, works, republished, ruling, popular, published.

25 интересных фактов об Ахматовой

Исраилова Гульнара Мамаджановна

Преподаватель Кокандского государственного педагогического института

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается об интересных фактах об Ахматовой. Она активно преследовалась, не допускалась к публикациям, ее родственники подвергались преследованиям и притеснениям. Ее творчество отражает все страдания, которые пережили не только люди, которых правящая партия считала «врагами народа», но и их семьи.

Ключевые слова: родственники, тяжелая жизнь, произведения, переизданные, правящие, популярные, опубликованные

Axmatova haqida 25 ta qiziqarli fakt

Isroilova Gulnora Mamadjanovna

Qo‘qon davlat pedagogika instituti o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Axmatova haqidagi qiziqarli faktlar haqida so'z boradi. U faol ta'qibga uchradi, nashr etishga ruxsat berilmadi va uning qarindoshlari ta'qib va ta'qiblarga duchor bo'ldi. Uning ijodida nafaqat hukmron partiya tomonidan "xalq dushmani" deb hisoblangan odamlar, balki ularning oilalari boshdan kechirgan barcha azob-uqubatlar aks etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qarindoshlar, og'ir hayot, asarlar, qayta nashr etilgan, hukmron, mashhur, nashr etilgan.

Poetess Anna Akhmatova lived a hard life. She was actively hounded, not allowed to publish, and her relatives were persecuted and harassed. Her work reflects all the suffering that not only people who were considered “enemies of the people” by the ruling party went through, but also their families. Even after the death of the poetess, her works were not published for a long time, and she was rehabilitated only long after she was gone.

She called herself a poet, not a poetess. Anna Akhmatova could not stand the word “poetess”, and was very angry if someone called her that.

Anna Akhmatova is a pseudonym, her real last name is Gorenko. But her father was categorically against his daughter’s passion for literature, and forbade her to use her family name.

All her life, Akhmatova was embarrassed by her first work. She called her early ballad poems, published, republished and very popular, "poor poems of a most empty girl" and did not like to remember them.

Once, during a walk in the garden of Tsarskoye Selo, she found a pin in the shape of a lyre. All her life, Anna Akhmatova believed that this pin was once dropped here by A.S. Pushkin himself.

Anna grew up in an unusual family. There were almost no books in the house, although her mother knew many poems by Derzhavin and Nekrasov by heart. Probably, this is partly why she became interested in literature from childhood.

In the short biography of Anna Akhmatova, it is reflected that in childhood she suffered from a serious illness, presumably smallpox. The illness left her deaf for some time, and it was after her recovery that she began to write poetry.

In the spring of 1910, the Italian artist Modigliani met a very young, but already married Anna Andreyevna in Paris. The romance lasted until August 1911, after which they never met again. However, this time gave the artist so much inspiration that during this year he painted many pictures, dedicating them all to his beloved.

The poetess survived two World Wars, and her two husbands and son were repressed after the revolution in Russia.

She tried with all her might to save her exiled son, Lev Gumilyov, and even wrote a cycle glorifying the Soviet power, "Glory to Peace", but all her attempts were unsuccessful. Her son was released in 1943, but was rehabilitated only in 1956, and he accused his mother of inaction, which was a heavy blow for her

According to Anna Akhmatova's own memoirs, she was a "wild girl", loved to walk barefoot and swim in the sea in any weather. Such behavior for a young lady in that era was considered unacceptable.

Already in childhood, the poetess mastered French at a high level.

In 1939, she was accepted into the Union of Soviet Writers, from where she was expelled in 1946, and five years later reinstated.

Anna Akhmatova was nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature twice, in 1965 and 1966, but this became known only 50 years later. It turned out that Akhmatova's candidacy was nominated by professors of Slavic languages Gunnar Jacobsson from the University of Gothenburg and Roman Jakobson from Harvard.

Akhmatova wrote her first poem at the age of 11. After rereading it "with a fresh mind", she realized that she needed to improve her art of versification, which she began to actively do.

A year before her death, in 1965, Anna Akhmatova visited Great Britain and became an honorary doctor of Oxford University (see interesting facts about Great Britain).

Throughout her life, she kept a diary. However, it became known only 7 years after the poetess's death, when it was accidentally discovered.

In addition to composing her own poems, A. Akhmatova also translated foreign poetry into Russian.

Recognized as a classic of Russian poetry back in the 1920s, Akhmatova was subjected to silence, censorship and persecution. At the same time, her name was surrounded by fame among poetry admirers both in the USSR and in exile during her lifetime.

In the USSR, many of her works were not published not only during Anna Akhmatova's lifetime, but also for about twenty years after her death.

Akhmatova's last collection of poems was published in 1925. After that, the NKVD did not allow any of this poetess's work to be published and called it "provocative and anti-communist".

For a long time, the poetess was under the supervision of the NKVD. Researchers of Akhmatova's biography believe that she was followed by the writer Sofia Ostrovskaya, whom the poetess considered her close friend, not knowing that she worked for the NKVD.

The poetess's first husband was the later repressed Nikolai Gumilyov, who sought her hand for a long time. Moreover, none of his relatives showed up for the wedding - they were all against this marriage and believed that it would not last long (see interesting facts about Gumilyov).

Streets in Kaliningrad, Odessa and Kyiv are named after the poetess. In addition, on June 25 of each year in the village of Komarovo there are Akhmatova Memorial Evenings, timed to coincide with Anna Akhmatova's birthday.

The poetess also wrote literary articles, very serious and profound. They were mainly devoted to the works of Pushkin and Lermontov.

Akhmatova was very superstitious all her life. Thus, she initially refused Gumilyov, who asked for her hand, because during a walk along the beach they came across two dolphins that had washed up on the shore. The poetess considered this a bad sign.

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